

DENTAL IN CHILDREN WITH TRAUMATIC STOMATITIS COMPLEX DENTAL TREATMENT OF DISEASES AND THEIR EVALUATION OF PREVENTION

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ABSTRACT

Pathological changes in the physico-biochemical state of the oral fluid of children with traumatic stomatitis are a fairly wide complex of other expressed changes in the oral cavity of sick children, together with the effect of a general somatic disease, they aggravate the pathological changes defined in the organs of the oral cavity to introduce treatment-prophylactic complex directions aimed at eliminating and preventing cases of deepening of the main traumatic stomatitis symptoms, creating a closed circle with an interdependent effect.

A low and very low level of oral hygiene is revealed, and the lack of knowledge on the rules of oral care among children and their parents deepens the situation. Pathological changes in the physico-biochemical state of the oral fluid of children with traumatic stomatitis are a wide enough complex of other expressed shifts in the oral cavity of sick children, together with the effect of a general somatic disease, aggravate the pathological changes noted in the organs of the oral cavity. In turn, the clinicopathological changes expressed in the oral cavity deepen the transition of the main traumatic stomatitis symptoms, creating a closed circle that has an interrelated effect on the course of these diseases. Depending on the severity of the main disease, the duration of treatment can be extended from 12 to 15 days, at least 2 times a year, due to the fact that children have to undergo treatment for a long time. Therefore, it is necessary to organize dental treatment-prophylactic measures in the conditions of treatment for children of this category. In this case, specialists should create an individual dental treatment-prophylactic complex for children with traumatic stomatitis, which is carried out against the background of treatment of the main disease. For children suffering from traumatic stomatitis, we have created a treatment-prophylaxis dental complex.

The following indicators were used as efficiency criteria of the developed dental treatment-prophylaxis complex:

1. Raising the level of oral hygiene in sick children;
2. To develop the skills of oral hygiene and to the child's mind absorb;
3. Reducing inflammation in periodontal soft tissues;

4. Restoration of pathological shifts in the physical and chemical state of mixed saliva;
5. Clinical speed of children tooth enamel strengthening and enamel remineralization recovery;
6. Reducing the level of dental caries

Research methods: The proposed dental treatment-prophylaxis complex has 6 directions:

1. Improving the level of hygiene in the oral cavity;
2. Anti-inflammatory;
3. Prevents caries;
4. Practical restorative treatment of caries;
5. Increasing the rate of saliva secretion (SST);
6. Remineralizing therapy.

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2. To develop the skills of oral hygiene and to the child's mind absorb;
3. Reducing inflammation in periodontal soft tissues;
4. Restoration of pathological shifts in the physical and chemical state of mixed saliva;
5. Children's tooth enamel strengthening and clinical speed of enamel remineralization restoration;
6. Reducing the level of dental caries.

Results of the study: In a study conducted on 15 children with traumatic stomatitis, oral hygiene was improved, various inflammations, caries prevention agents and caries complications, REM therapy and comprehensive measures implemented in cases of low salivary secretion rate were improved in children and as a result of explanatory work carried out in their parents regarding the rules of care of the oral cavity, relief from traumatic stomatitis was achieved.

Conclusion: Traumatic inflammations of the oral mucosa have a very diverse appearance: from catarrhal inflammation to ulcerative or hyperplastic manifestations. The cause of injury can also be external traumatic factors, local defects and deformations of teeth. Also, careless dental practice or restless behavior of the patient can be an etiological effect. Young children require special attention, in whom it is very difficult to diagnose and treat diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. Knowing the clinical manifestations of traumatic injuries of the mucous membrane allows choosing the optimal medical tactics in each clinical case.

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